

METHODS OF FORMATION AND DETERMINATION OF POTENTIAL IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Abstract: *Information Technology to adequately study and formulate their thinking skills in this field. Because, as the day goes by, Information Systems, which are fundamental for information technology, are constantly developing and being enriched with various modes, technologies. This requires repeated study and a certain amount of time, if the potential for knowledge and skills learned in the school is not formed.*

Key words: *information technology, virtual laboratory, workshop, modeling packages, innovation, information, educational and methodical material, learning tools, multimedia.*

One of the main factors of the educational system and process is the expression from which the reader develops their thinking along with providing fundamental knowledge to the youth. Today, in the world, we can meet a huge number of, sinfual resources on the formation and identification of potential in a classified form. For example, testometrika.com, globalintelligentsia.com web portals can be accessed. These portals contain 11 types of testing issues, the most common method of testing is IQ testing. IQ (intelligence quotient), which means the stage of intelligence, the factor of the development of the mind, or intellektual potential [5].The study of the issues of radical reform of the education system, especially effective organization of educational processes in secondary schools and expansion of thinking skills of students in our republic are considered one of the important issues. Also in the world, knowledge of

the IT industry, the electronic government system, the computer systems and services of society, the full-blooded and rational use of State interactive services are considered important indicators. For this purpose, it is one of the pressing issues in our republic that awaits the solution of the general secondary school students in the education of Information Technology to adequately study and formulate their thinking skills in this field. Because, as the day goes by, Information Systems, which are fundamental for information technology, are constantly developing and being enriched with various modes, technologies. This requires repeated study and a certain amount of time, if the potential for knowledge and skills learned in the school is not formed.

In information technology, there are a number of net methods for performing a certain specific task. For example, there are 7 different ways to launch a simple text editor. The question arises, Should students be taught these 7 methods in Information Technology Education in general secondary education system? Or do you want to launch a text editor with intellectual potential based on a specific knowledge and skills? Of course, the teaching of 7 methods in this matter limits the knowledge and opportunity of the student, and when changes in the Information System occur, it seems that knowledge and skills are not enough. If, on the basis of a certain knowledge and skill, the student is taught to perform this task by employing intellectual capacity, then in the future he will never stop.

One of the most complex processes in the educational system is the lesson. If we compare the lesson to the sun, the planets around it-these are the methods and means of teaching[3]. Similarly, there are also subjects and objects of the lesson, namely participants, tools, methods and methods of teaching, forms of teaching. Information Technology Education in general secondary education, that is, the subject of Computer Science and information technology, as well as other subjects, we cite the above-mentioned elements.

Computer Engineering is introduced into the spectrum of participants in the subject of Informatics and Information Technology, which means that there is an effect of the element in the subject. Computer technology can also be used in other subjects, but in it this technique enters the spectrum of tools. In this regard, the subject of Information Technology Education in secondary schools in general should take into account the position of computer technology in the teaching of Informatics and Information Technology. This can be the most necessary participant in the formation and determination of the intellectual potential of the developing learner.

In the educational system, a lot of scientific and methodological research is being carried out on the formation of potential. These are done mainly due to the fact that each school subject and each subject has its own characteristics. The subjects and objects of the above lesson, that is, participants, supplies, as well as affect the choice of methods and methods.

The theory of Kettell-Horn-Carol is widely used in the world and is one of its own theories for the emergence of the psychosocial and didactic of young people, the formation of actual potential[7]. This theory gives a broader interpretation of the psychological theory of the structure of cognitive abilities of students, and at the same time it is aimed at developing the intellectual potential of the learner by combining the theory of three major theorists Raymond Kettell, John Horn and John Carols[10]. This theory has been proven to be important for people engaged in self-education based on the results of numerous methodological studies over the last years of the 20th century[8].

Kettell-Horn-Carol's theory is two, Kettell-Horn's theory of flexibility and cognitive detection intelligence is Carol's theory of three levels of Cognitive Ability[2]. Both theories have close similarities, which helped to combine these theories among themselves. Method for the formation of multi-intellectual capacity based on the analysis of scientific and applied works, the definition of flexibility and knowledge intellect is divided into:

Flexible intelligence includes the following abilities and qualities:

1. To learn.
2. Mavhum (abstract) thinking ability.
3. Ability to interact, find and identify laws, systematize information obtained, analyze and process new knowledge.
4. Ability to adapt to new conditions, flexibility.
5. Deductive and inductive thinking ability.
6. Ability to solve problems encountered for the first time
7. Use new approaches to solving problems that were previously obvious.
8. Ability to remember. In most cases, flexibility is important for Intel's level of development.

The period of development of most of these skills and qualities rises to the highest peak of school age in general secondary education. After that, its level begins to gradually decrease[5].

Intelligence of knowledge detection (BAI) is a method and method of determining the previously accumulated knowledge and skills, ability to

apply. BAI is responsible for the knowledge and skills that remain in the long-term memory that engages flexible intelligence and uses it in practice. It includes the following:

1. Words related to the sphere (dictionary).
2. Ability to solve problems by methods previously known and tested in the experiment.
3. The basis of general knowledge (interdependence of subjects and fundamental subjects), knowledge of the field.

According to scientists, the level of BAI in different and different areas is different. For example, taking the use of Information Technology, a programmer, a system administrator, can be useful.

Bai's commitment to flexibility is that the faster it learns, the more knowledge and knowledge it can be acquired, the more knowledge capacity and annual capacity it will have.

The Nobel Prize winner, James Heckman, professor at the University of Chicago (James Heckman), argues that economic systems are related to human abilities and skills (human skills) [4]. According to the scientist, any large economy is based on the development of skills, knowledge, abilities and skills of citizens. According to the scientist's account, at least 13 percent of the costs incurred for early education will "return to society" in the future. The development of social skills in children from an early age along with cognitive abilities leads to the emergence of citizens who will benefit society in the future.

According to Uzbek scientists, the socio-psychological factors of the formation of independent thinking, creative abilities in the students form and determine the peculiarities of intellectual potential through independent thinking, formation of creative thinking through interactive educational methods that motivate independent thinking, as well as cognitive approaches in the educational process[3].

Based on the above, it is necessary to pay great attention to cognitive abilities in secondary schools in general. Especially today, within the framework of e-government, every graduate of the school is in a certain sense a requirement for a period of determining flexibility and knowledge within the framework of Information Technology Education, focusing on the content and process of education on cognitive abilities.

Igor Boltovnin believes that the levels of cognitive abilities are different, and Carroll put forward the idea of three cognitive stages [2]:

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